

Workflows and Guidelines for Research Data: Key Insights from Use Cases and Adaptation Suggestions

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This document serves as a summary of the use cases carried out by the [Research Data Management \(RDM\) Network of the University of Basel](#) as part of the swissuniversities-funded project ‘[Advancement of the Data Stewardship Program and Research Data Management Support at the University of Basel](#)’, together with the [Institute for Biomedical Ethics \(IBMB\)](#), the [Institute of Nursing Science \(INS\)](#), and the [Department for Pharmaceutical Sciences \(DPhW\)](#) at the University of Basel. The goal of the use cases was to develop RDM workflows and guidelines for specific data types that incorporate the university’s new [data and information classification](#).

This document provides a **summary of the use case process, key insights and lessons learned** from the workshops and feedback sessions with the researchers involved, as well as **adaptation suggestions** for reuse of the developed workflows and guidelines for other research units at the University of Basel and beyond.

For further questions or support, contact the [coordination team](#) of the [RDM Network](#).

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Summary of use case procedure

Each use case involved 3–5 researchers from 1–2 research groups. The use cases were organized in cooperation with the [data stewards](#) in the respective subject areas:

- [Biomedical Ethics \(IBMB\)](#), together with Tenzin Wangmo on the data type “*qualitative data from interviews and focus groups*”
- [Nursing Science \(INS\)](#), together with Sarah N. Musy on the data type “*routine data form healthcare providers*”
- [Pharmaceutical Sciences \(DPhW\)](#), together with Eliane Garo on the data type “*digital survey data*”

For each use case, two workshops were held to develop the workflows and guidelines in collaboration with researchers who work with the respective data types. The **first workshop** served as a status quo analysis of current practices along the RDM lifecycle. Researchers explained how they manage the data type in their daily work, including the work steps involved, the tools used, and the challenges encountered. The members of the RDM network then provided feedback and identified gaps, risks and opportunities for improvement.

Between workshops, an initial draft for workflows and guidelines was developed in consultation with experts from the RDM Network. The second workshop was carried out to get feedback on the documents from the researchers involved, and to identify remaining gaps and potential improvements. The feedback gathered was then used to develop a final version of the documents. The resulting workflows and guidelines were eventually presented in the respective organizational units to inform fellow researchers and to support their implementation.

Key Insights and Lessons Learned

- Direct collaboration with researchers and **tailoring RDM practices to their specific needs** (rather than abstract concepts) were particularly valued, both by the RDM network and by the researchers. Researchers themselves defined the document requirements; therefore workflows and guidelines aligned with research reality.
- **Visualizing workflow phases** proved especially helpful for clarity:
 - RDM lifecycle commonalities: Project phases and certain content elements (e.g., data organization, publication, project end) are similarly structured for many data types.
 - Different document formats evolved per research unit (see *Image 1*):
 - *DPhW*: One workflow document and one guidelines document was generated.
 - *IBMB*: The document includes an overarching workflow diagram for all project phases, along with five phase-specific sections featuring comment fields to track completed processes in joint projects. It serves as an active documentation tool.
 - *INS*: The workflows and guidelines were developed as an integrated document using Quarto with PDF output. It features an overarching workflow diagram for the entire RDM lifecycle as well as phase-specific workflow diagrams at the start of each major section. The workflow diagrams were created using Mermaid and embedded directly into the guideline document.

Image 1: Different workflow formats evolved per research unit.

- Addressing **more than one data type per use case proved challenging**. While it initially seemed efficient to address several data types simultaneously, workshop discussions repeatedly demonstrated that sufficient time for reflection, knowledge exchange, and discussion of RDM practices was more valuable than broadening the scope to additional data types.

- **Knowledge of RDM** among workshop participants was highly **heterogeneous** at the beginning of the first workshop:
 - Roles and responsibilities were not always clearly defined or actively reflected upon. Even within research groups, processes were often unclear, even when standard operating procedures (SOP) existed (which were frequently outdated due to time or staff shortages). In particular, end-of-project activities, such as data cleaning, mid/long-term storage, and project closure, often lacked clear procedures.
 - Applying the University of Basel's new [data and information classification](#) caused significant uncertainty and was one of the topics that created the most discussion during the workshops. Many researchers were either unaware of the framework or unsure how to apply it to their own projects. Questions arose, e.g., regarding the selection of permitted tools or the correct processing and storage of data for the respective protection classes.
 - Discussions frequently revealed uncertainty around key data protection concepts. In particular, researchers were often unsure about the differences between anonymized and pseudonymized data, personal and sensitive data, and direct and indirect identifiers.
 - There was uncertainty regarding the required documentation, submission deadlines, and the specific ethics committee responsible when preparing ethics applications.
 - Metadata and their standards were unfamiliar to some participants.
 - There were no standardized documentation guidelines (everyone documented at their own discretion), and versioning processes were barely established.
 - Data publication was unfamiliar to many researchers; group leaders had the most experience.
 - Data Access Committees (DAC) were also largely unknown. Publishing Class III data or its metadata were often not pursued, partly due to concerns about repository security.

- **Researchers found** the following **particularly valuable**:
 - Being guided and supported throughout the entire process. The project's structured timeline and external expertise enabled the creation of documents that had long been desired but previously lacked the necessary time and resources.
 - A clear table of roles and responsibilities, both within the group and project context. This includes the introduction of regular "Data Cleaning Days" (dedicated sessions for organizing and cleaning research data) for the whole research group.
 - A visual representation of the workflow across all project phases as well as the accompanying detailed guidelines documents, which is especially helpful at the start of a project (e.g., for new PhD students to enable forward planning).
 - Guidance on how to address data protection and ethics issues.
 - A unified list of tools used for documentation, data acquisition and data processing for the whole research group.
 - A standardized end-of-project workflow (including handover document and exit interview).
 - The development of practical templates, e.g. README files, version history logs, or descriptions of project roles and responsibilities, which helped translate RDM recommendations into concrete actions and lowered the barrier to implementing good documentation practices.

- **Recommendations for future handling and revision of documents**:
 - We recommend scheduling regular document reviews with research groups. Researchers should ultimately update documents based on their needs, which works best when RDM roles and responsibilities are clearly communicated (e.g., by group leaders).
 - We also recommend ensuring that links remain up to date (especially when DOIs or permalinks are unavailable).

Adaptation Suggestions

Important:

Co-develop workflows with researchers rather than simply handing them finished guidelines to implement. Consider a joint workshop to streamline the adaptation process.

Content analysis:

Scan the workflow and guidelines to distinguish between general RDM information and data type- or research unit-specific content (see Image 2).

Excerpt from DPhW Guidelines document:

1.5 Base organization for data storage and research documentation

Set up a base organization for how you store your data and document your research process.

- **Storage:** use the U-drive for data storage. The U-drive enables automatic data backups and is managed by the university's IT services.
- **Data and File Organization:**
 - **Folder Structure:** Use the structure for "Study Folder" that is provided in the SOP-QA-1 Start up Study.
 - **File Naming:** Use consistent and descriptive file names, including dates and version numbers. Follow the naming conventions of the PCRG: <Date YYYYMMDD>_<Study Acronym>_<Title of document>_<Draft or Final>_<Version Number>. See SOP-QA-3 Good Documentation Practice.
- **Documentation:** Choose a research notebook for documenting your research process. Do not store data class 2/3 in your research notebook. For daily research documentation, use
 - **OneNote, and save it on U-drive** (do not store in cloud)
 - If you cannot avoid storing data class 2/3 in your research notebook, password-protect sections of your notebook (data class 2), or use encryption tools like Cryptomator or VeraCrypt (data class 3). ITS provide a detailed description on how to use Cryptomator
 - **ELN-Wiki from the Biozentrum**
 - Only allowed for Data class 0-2. Do not store class 3 data in the Wiki.

Image 2: Example workflow section (Planning), highlighting data type-specific (red) and general RDM information (green) within the DPhW workflow. Please note that general RDM information is still specific to the University of Basel.

Leverage the modular design:

Use the workflows and guidelines as an "idea book" with adaptable workflow elements and text blocks.

- Start with section headers ('planning', 'data collection', etc.) as entry points to navigate the documents.
- For each section, work with researchers from your research team to:
 - Identify key aspects relevant to your research.
 - Determine what can be directly adopted from the workflows and guidelines, and what needs modification.
 - Identify gaps, challenges and needs in your current project workflow and use solutions from use cases as guidance.

Adapt systematically:

- Keep general RDM sections as your stable foundation.
- Modify data type-specific sections to fit your data type(s).
- Adjust tool recommendations to your infrastructure.
- Update role definitions to match your team structure.
- Align compliance requirements with your institutional policies.
- Create templates for commonly used files.

Document adaptations:

Track all future changes in a single document for reference and version control. Include feedback, comments, or tracked changes in this file. For a clean version, use tools like LaTeX or Quarto, and manage versions with Git.